

NATURAL DISASTERS AND THEIR CAUSES

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Abstract. *Opinions on natural disasters. The occurrence or recurrence of natural disasters in different parts of the planet has been highlighted. Depending on the type and location of the disaster, each state or region should develop its own evacuation measures. Not only economic benefits and convenience, but also the possibility of natural disasters were written in the construction planning process.*

Keywords: *natural disaster, endogenous, exogenous, volcano, earthquake, hurricane, tsunami, anthropogenic, technogenic, nuclear power plant, typhoon, tornado, snowstorm.*

ПРИРОДНЫЕ БЕДСТВИЯ И ИХ ПРИЧИНЫ

Аннотация. *Мнения о стихийных бедствиях. Освещено возникновение или повторяемость природных катаклизмов в различных частях планеты. В зависимости от типа и места катастрофы каждый штат или регион должен разработать свои собственные меры эвакуации. В процессе планирования строительства были прописаны не только экономическая выгода и удобство, но и возможность стихийных бедствий.*

Ключевые слова: *стихийное бедствие, эндогенное, экзогенное, вулкан, землетрясение, ураган, цунами, антропогенное, техногенное, атомная электростанция, тайфун, смерч, метель.*

Enter. A natural disaster is a natural phenomenon that has an extraordinary nature and leads to the disruption of normal activities of the population, the death of people, and the destruction of material wealth. Natural disasters can occur both independently and interdependently: one of them can lead to another. Some of them often occur during human activities (for example, forest and peat fires, industrial explosions in mountainous areas, construction of dams, digging (exploitation) of quarries, which often It leads to landslides, avalanches, and the collapse of glaciers.

Natural disasters play a big role in the development of our planet natural disasters cause incredible damage to the geosystem, human civilization, but we must admit that the contribution of these natural disasters (endogenous, exogenous) to the earth's evaluation is immeasurable We know very well that these processes are capable of creating a new form of life along with

extinction. At this time when the natural processes on the earth threaten the civilization of mankind, hundreds of anthropogenic factors contribute to the acceleration and repetition of these processes.

Not only the internal and external forces of the earth, but also the influence of anthropogenic factors are felt in the occurrence of natural disasters. First of all, let's define a natural disaster: it is an unexpected, uncontrollable, high-speed force that causes heavy catastrophe and victims, natural and economic damage. Natural disasters occur under the influence of the internal forces of the Earth, fracturing, displacement of the earth's crust, volcanic eruptions, and gravity (meteorites falling). Looking at the history of the Earth, we can see that natural disasters millions of years ago were very large-scale, powerful and more destructive than today. In the course of the internal reconstruction of our planet, many disasters have been observed since now, and by our time, the earth is living its life in a rather suspended situation.

Natural disasters can be divided into the following types according to their origin:

1) endogenous - under the influence of the internal energy and strength of the earth, these can include earthquakes, tsunamis, volcanic eruptions;

2) exogenous - mainly solar energy and solar activity, storms of the atmosphere, hydrosphere and gravity field, examples of which are cyclones, hurricanes, floods, thunderstorms, landslides, droughts, sandstorms;

3) a separate group of anthropogenic disasters, that is, disasters caused by mankind. It is caused by human activity, but the force of occurrence is internal or external forces. [1]

Natural disasters can be divided into certain groups depending on the time of their occurrence, that is, they can be classified according to the time of impact on a certain natural system.

1. Short-term natural disasters that occur suddenly and unexpectedly. These include earthquakes, avalanches, and volcanic eruptions.

2. Natural disasters that occur as a result of the accumulation of the effects of some negative events over a long period of time. These concepts, familiar to all of us, are anthropogenic impact, man-made impact related to pollution of the atmosphere, lithosphere and hydrosphere. Such a crisis can be explained by the increase in the population of the earth. If we list the disasters that arise in this way, these are the problems of famine and water shortage.

This process, which has been going on for a long time to this day, is already felt in the great deed of our planet. This will inevitably lead to a global environmental crisis. Because at a time when there is a need to feed, heat, meet the household and cultural needs of a large population, it is necessary to develop new lands, extract useful mineral resources, and the sharp growth of

agglomerations and megacities, and this affects the environment and our planet. increases the pressure.

3. There is also a type of natural disaster that occurs suddenly, but it is difficult to get rid of its complications for a long time. Let's take an example of the explosion at the nuclear power plant (Chernobyl). The scale of casualties and impacts of such an explosion left a mark unmatched by any other natural disaster, or the detonation of atomic bombs in Japan (Hiroshima and Nagasaki).

The main part. Different types of disasters occur in different regions, depending on the influence of natural disasters. For example, a tsunami or tornado is not a threat to inland continental countries. Or, as the central part of the solid plates is less likely to have volcanic eruptions or earthquakes, guidelines for dealing with natural disasters are developed according to the location of countries. Security measures or evacuation routes developed for a certain country are unique to that country (individual) and are not suitable for all countries. The first reason for this is geographical location, and factors such as relief and climate also play an important role. If tsunamis, typhoons, and tornadoes threaten the countries of North America, Southeast Asia, and the Indian Ocean basin, earthquakes and volcanic eruptions threaten the peace of countries located in the Pacific Ring of Fire, the countries of the Alpine-Himalaya region, and the Caribbean Sea basin. As an example of our thoughts, we give examples of disasters that caused huge material and moral losses. On January 12, 2010, at 16:53 local time, a terrible earthquake was observed in Haiti, an island located in the Caribbean Sea. The epicenter of the earthquake occurred 22 kilometers southwest of the capital of the Republic of Haiti, Port-au-Prince, at a depth of 13 kilometers. The strongest earthquake observed was 7-point magnitude and 5-point tremors were repeated over 15 mats.

According to official data, 222,570 people died, more than 311,000 were injured, and 869 were missing. The material damage was estimated at 5.6 billion euros. Another major earthquake occurred in Kashmir on October 8, 2005 at 8:50 a.m. Pakistan time. The epicenter of the earthquake was in the part of Kashmir administered by Pakistan, and the intensity of the earthquake was 7-6 on the Richter scale. This disaster caused significant damage to the north-east of Pakistan, Afghanistan and the northern regions of India. Muzaffarabad, the center of Azad-Kashmir, was almost completely destroyed (more than 70%), 11 thousand people died. It is no exaggeration to say that many villages and towns were destroyed and disappeared from the face of the earth.

Among these are Margala Towers, Balakot city, Garhi Habibull, Rawalakot. Uri and Jammu and Kashmir states suffered \$1,500 damage in the territory of India. This earthquake is considered the worst in South Asia in the last 100 years, and the total damage to Pakistan was 12

billion US dollars. The earthquake that occurred in the Indian Ocean on December 26, 2004 caused the most deadly tsunami.

The magnitude of the earthquake was estimated from 9.1 to 9.3 points, and the epicenter of the earthquake was located in the Indian Ocean in the north of Samuel Island, near the northwestern coast of Sumatra Island. The tsunami reached Indonesia, Sri Lanka and southern India, Thailand and several other coastal countries. The wave height was more than 15 meters and caused a lot of destruction and death of people, and even destroyed the port of Elizabeth, located in the Republic of South Africa (6900 km from the epicenter). According to various sources, 225,000 to 300,000 people died. In the process of writing the article, the event that made me think that it is inappropriate to always envy landlocked countries because of their favorable economic geographical position, was the 9.0-9.1 magnitude earthquake on the coast of the Japanese island of Honshu on March 11, 2011, 70 km from Japan. occurred in the distance, and as a result of the Earthquake, a strong tsunami was generated. According to official data, 15,896 people were killed, 2,536 were missing, and 6,157 were injured. A man-made factor contributed to the increase in the damage caused by the natural disaster, that is, an accident occurred at the Fukushima Nuclear Power Plant. As a result, the number of victims and irradiated people in the radioactive area increased. The total material damage caused by this earthquake was estimated at 15-16 trillion yen (198-309 billion US dollars). The hurricane that caused the greatest damage in the history of the United States was called "Katrina" and was rated as category 5-6 on the Saffira-Simpson scale.

This disaster happened at the end of August 2005. New Orleans and Louisiana suffered the most damage, meaning that 80% of residential areas were flooded. A snowstorm in Afghanistan resulted in temperatures falling below -30°C , resulting in 180cm of snow in the foothills and killing 1.337 million people, with 100 more people in hospitals as a result of the cold war. more than 100,000 sheep and goats and 315,000 cattle were killed. In February and March 2000, floods in Mozambique were caused by five weeks of heavy rain that left many people homeless. It caused the death of more than 700 people, the washing away of the fertile layer of 1,400 square km, and the displacement of 20,000 cattle and sheep herds.

Summary. We can give hundreds of examples of natural disasters that have occurred in the history of mankind, which we have mentioned above and many more. As we are the children of this mother earth, we should not complain about nature's anger or whims, but we need to work out how to weaken the force of damage and develop measures to eliminate it. We must conclude that every building, structure, and city under construction is not only aimed at comfort and economic efficiency for mankind, but we must take into account the "surprises" of our motherland.

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